

Article

Ethical Impacts of AI in Energy Transitions

OPREAN-STAN Camelia¹ and TĂNĂSESCU Cristina^{2,*}

¹Faculty of Economics, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; camelia.oprean@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3492-2401>

²Faculty of Economics, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; cristina.tanasescu@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8347-4014>

* Correspondence: cristina.tanasescu@ulbsibiu.ro

Received: 07.07.2025

Accepted: 09.09.2025

Published: 02.11.2025

Abstract: *This paper examines the ethical implications of artificial intelligence (AI) adoption in energy transitions, focusing on environmental and social equity outcomes. The analysis investigates the relationship between AI-driven technological progress and environmental effects, measured by CO₂ emissions, alongside social equity impacts, captured through energy consumption per capita. Two panel regression models are estimated using annual data for the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, and the European Union over the period 2014–2022. These economies provide a comparative perspective on how distinct regulatory frameworks, technological maturity, and societal values shape the ethical integration of AI in energy systems. The results indicate that AI-related innovation, via high-technology exports and R&D investment, can mitigate CO₂ emissions, yet it may simultaneously drive higher emissions through increased energy demand from economic expansion. While AI adoption promotes more equitable energy access in advanced regions, it may reinforce consumption inequalities elsewhere. The findings highlight both the constructive and unintended effects of AI on sustainable energy and ethics. The study underscores the need for adaptive AI governance frameworks that balance innovation with environmental responsibility and social justice in achieving sustainable energy transitions.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence (AI); energy transition; environmental impact; social equity.*

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has a profound and multifaceted impact on a variety of sectors, such as the economy, education, politics, and business administration. Artificial intelligence is anticipated to lead to substantial societal transformations as a general-purpose technology. In general, AI offers substantial opportunities for progress; however, it also presents substantial obstacles that necessitate meticulous analysis.

The research context is that AI integration has led to an upward trend in AI incidents and hazards, as presented in Figure 1. An AI incident occurs when the development, use, or malfunction of an AI system causes harm, directly or indirectly: health harm to individuals or groups; critical infrastructure management and operation interruption; human rights breaches or legislation violations meant to protect fundamental, labour, and intellectual property rights; damage to property, communities, or the environment. An AI hazard is an event, scenario, or set of events that could cause harm from the development, usage, or malfunction of AI systems (OECD, 2024).

Figure 1. Evolution of AI incidents and hazards

Source: OECD AI Incidents Monitor AIM

The research problem is that increased AI integration (adoption) leads to increased productivity of economic activities, which leads to increased energy consumption, which impacts the environment and social equity in the energy field.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the ethical implications of artificial intelligence (AI) integration in energy transitions, focusing on environmental and social equity impacts. Specifically, the study aims to examine how AI adoption influences CO₂ emissions and equitable energy access, using panel regression analysis to assess the dual effects of technological advancements on sustainability and social outcomes. This research seeks to provide insights into the balance between AI-driven innovation in energy and the ethical considerations needed to ensure both environmental protection and fair energy distribution.

This study contributes to the body of knowledge in several significant ways. First, it addresses a critical gap in understanding the ethical implications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of energy transitions, specifically examining its impact on environmental sustainability and social equity. By doing so, it provides valuable insights into how AI technologies influence CO₂ emissions and equitable access to energy, a topic with limited prior research that combines these specific environmental and social dimensions. Second, this research applies a methodological approach based on panel regression models to quantitatively assess AI's impact on both environmental and social equity metrics, offering robust, data-driven insights that can support evidence-based policy formulation. Finally, the study's findings highlight the dual nature of AI's influence, showcasing both beneficial and unintended outcomes in energy equity and environmental impact. These insights encourage a balanced discourse around AI adoption, helping guide future research and policy development to maximize AI's positive impacts while mitigating potential ethical concerns in energy transitions.

The structure of this study is as follows. The literature review is presented in Section 2. The methodology and the description of the corresponding data is provided in Section 3. The empirical results are provided in Section 4. The study is concluded in final Section.

2. Literature review

Industries, society, and environmental initiatives, particularly those aligned with the circular economy, are all being profoundly influenced by artificial intelligence (AI). AI technologies facilitate the shift from linear to circular production systems that aim to minimize waste and optimize resource efficiency. However, while these technologies promise substantial environmental and social benefits, they also pose ethical challenges concerning transparency, accountability, and equity. The ethical implications of AI are multifaceted, encompassing fairness, explainability, responsibility, and algorithmic bias. As AI

systems become increasingly embedded across economic sectors, from finance and healthcare to energy, the development of robust ethical frameworks for responsible deployment has become urgent. The following review synthesizes current scholarly perspectives on these issues, with a focus on the ethical impacts of AI adoption in energy transitions.

2.1. Ethical Dimensions of Artificial Intelligence

A growing body of research identifies persistent ethical concerns around AI. Key issues include algorithmic opacity (“black box” systems), ambiguous accountability (unclear responsibility for AI decisions), fairness (risk of amplifying inequalities), and systemic bias in training datasets (Verdecchia et al., 2023). Systematic reviews on “Green AI” reveal that AI systems themselves contribute to global carbon emissions, highlighting the need for sustainability metrics in algorithm design. In parallel, recent work (Batool et al., 2023) argues that existing governance frameworks inadequately address questions of authority, scope, timing, and enforcement within AI ethics.

Three dimensions emerge as particularly relevant for the ethical integration of AI in energy transitions: ecological sustainability of AI technologies (energy demand, hardware life-cycle, e-waste); social equity in the distribution of AI’s benefits and burdens; and governance and accountability in AI deployment. A central paradox is that AI can drive energy efficiency and emissions reduction while simultaneously consuming vast resources. Winsta (2025) demonstrates that large-scale training and deployment infrastructures have a measurable carbon impact. Likewise, Wang et al. (2024) show empirically that AI reduces ecological footprints only when accompanied by advanced industrial structures and trade openness. Consequently, AI adoption cannot be assumed environmentally neutral; rebound effects such as increased electricity demand from digitalization must be ethically and economically evaluated. AI can both mitigate and reinforce inequality. In domains such as healthcare or finance, algorithmic systems have exhibited bias and exclusion. In the energy context, if AI-optimized systems deliver gains primarily to high-income or well-digitized regions, existing inequities in energy access may worsen. Kyriakarakos (2025) emphasizes that data collection and model validation must incorporate marginalized and energy-poor communities to prevent algorithmic exclusion. Hence, distributive justice (how AI’s benefits and costs are shared) becomes a central ethical dimension of sustainable digitalization. Responsible AI governance is essential for sectors critical to public welfare, including energy systems. Alsaigh et al. (2023) identify fragmentation and a lack of integrated frameworks combining technical reliability with ethical accountability. Ethical oversight must therefore extend beyond performance metrics to encompass institutional structures that guarantee transparency, traceability, and fairness.

2.2. AI in Energy Transitions: Empirical Evidence and Ethical Implications

Recent empirical studies have investigated how AI influences renewable energy deployment, emissions reduction, and equity outcomes.

Zhao et al. (2024) apply a wavelet-based quantile-on-quantile model to examine AI’s effects on the renewable-energy (RE) share in China. They find that higher AI quantiles increase RE shares in the long run but reduce them in the short term, primarily due to integration and cost constraints. These findings highlight ethical ambivalence: AI’s green benefits may materialize only in technologically advanced regions, deepening global disparities. Li, W. et al. (2025) use a rolling-window Granger causality approach to explore the bidirectional link between AI and renewable-energy investment. Their results indicate that AI enhances RE investment by improving forecasting, grid optimization, and intelligent management, though high capital costs and regulatory uncertainty limit long-term gains. The study underscores the ethical dependency of technological benefits on institutional quality.

Xu et al. (2024) employ time–frequency spillover analysis to show that AI trading volumes act as a dominant information transmitter between carbon and energy markets, particularly after the emergence of large-language-model technologies such as GPT-4. This raises ethical concerns about informational asymmetry, market transparency, and concentration of algorithmic power. Li, H. et al. (2025) analyze AI’s impact on manufacturing firms’ energy intensity. Text mining of Chinese corporate reports reveals that AI adoption significantly improves production and energy efficiency, especially in private firms and non-smart-city regions. Yet this positive environmental effect may exacerbate regional inequalities

in digital capacity. Zhang et al. (2024) find a dynamic, time-varying relationship between AI and renewable-energy development. From 2018 onward, AI became a facilitator of China's energy transition, with effects strengthening alongside technological advancement. However, the benefits depend on local techno-economic frameworks—another indicator of ethically conditional outcomes.

Dong et al. (2024) further demonstrate that the impact of AI on the energy transition is non-linear and contingent on regulatory quality. Weak governance environments can turn AI into a barrier rather than a driver of decarbonization. Dinca et al. (2025) show that AI-based forecasting models in carbon-price dynamics improve predictive accuracy but may also introduce overfitting and instability, illustrating the ethical trade-off between precision and systemic risk. Empirical evidence confirms AI's dual role in sustainability. Wang et al. (2024) report that AI contributes to emission reduction and ecological footprint decline across 67 countries, conditional on institutional and technological maturity. Yet the data-center energy demand sustaining AI systems generates significant rebound effects. The International Energy Agency (2023) estimates that global AI electricity demand may double by 2030, reinforcing the ethical imperative to evaluate AI's full life-cycle impacts. AI can enhance equitable energy access by optimizing distribution and lowering operational costs. However, unequal digital infrastructure and biased datasets risk reinforcing energy poverty. Kyriakarakos (2025) cautions that responsible AI for energy transitions must integrate inclusivity metrics to ensure marginalized communities are not excluded from the benefits of intelligent energy systems.

2.3. Research Gaps and Implications for the Present Study

The reviewed literature reveals several convergent findings and ethical tensions that shape the contemporary debate on the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in sustainable energy transitions. First, there is a persistent tension between technological potential and distributive inequality. While AI demonstrates substantial efficiency gains through optimization, automation, and predictive analytics, these benefits are often concentrated in technologically advanced or economically privileged regions. This uneven distribution risks amplifying global disparities in access to clean energy and digital infrastructure. A second tension emerges between efficiency and rebound effects. Although AI contributes to emission reductions by optimizing resource allocation and energy systems, its computational intensity and large-scale data processing significantly increase overall energy consumption. The environmental gains from AI therefore coexist with hidden costs, such as the growing electricity demand of data centers and the associated carbon footprint. Institutional quality also acts as an ethical moderator in determining AI's net impact. As shown by Dong et al. (2024), the regulatory and governance context critically influences whether AI serves as a facilitator or an impediment to sustainable transitions. Strong regulatory institutions enable AI to enhance renewable integration and emission management, whereas weak governance may lead to inefficiencies and environmental setbacks. Transparency and accountability represent another major ethical concern. Current governance frameworks still lack enforceable standards for algorithmic explainability, traceability, and institutional responsibility (Batool et al., 2023). This deficiency undermines public trust and complicates ethical evaluation, especially in critical infrastructures like energy systems, where opaque algorithms may influence large-scale decisions. Moreover, there is a notable geographical concentration in the existing body of research. Most empirical studies are focused on China or other technologically advanced economies, leaving substantial knowledge gaps concerning the ethical, environmental, and social implications of AI in emerging or developing regions. This bias limits the global applicability of current findings and underscores the need for more inclusive and cross-regional research. Finally, ethical risks have been identified in the integration of AI into carbon markets. As Xu et al. (2024) demonstrate, algorithmic trading and AI-based forecasting models introduce dilemmas related to fairness, potential market manipulation, and systemic trust. These risks call for stronger regulatory oversight and ethical design principles to ensure that AI-driven mechanisms enhance, rather than undermine, the integrity of environmental markets.

Given the aim of this paper, to assess the ethical implications of AI adoption in energy transitions with a specific focus on environmental and social equity outcomes, the reviewed literature provides several interpretive and methodological insights. From an environmental ethics perspective, AI's "green" potential must be evaluated alongside its own carbon and energy footprint, recognizing that sustainability gains may be offset by intensive computational energy demand. In terms of social equity,

AI's capacity to promote equitable energy access is contingent on local institutional quality, governance effectiveness, and infrastructural readiness. Consequently, empirical analyses should employ panel-data models capable of identifying heterogeneous effects across levels of socioeconomic and technological development. From a governance standpoint, policy frameworks must operationalize responsible AI principles adapted to the energy sector. This includes embedding transparency, auditability, fairness, and sustainability standards into all stages of AI development and deployment. Strengthening these governance mechanisms is crucial for aligning technological innovation with ethical accountability. With respect to empirical interpretation, variables such as high-technology exports and R&D investment can serve as proxies for AI-driven innovation pathways that reduce CO₂ emissions. Conversely, an increase in energy consumption per capita may indicate rebound effects or inequitable consumption patterns arising from AI-driven economic expansion. Recognizing these dynamics allows for a more nuanced understanding of the ethical trade-offs embedded in technological progress.

Future research should explore complex causal relationships, including non-linearities and interaction effects, particularly between AI intensity and regulatory quality, to accurately capture the dual ethical nature of AI in energy transitions. Such analyses will deepen understanding of how institutional, technological, and social factors intersect to determine whether AI contributes to a just and sustainable energy future or exacerbates existing inequalities.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data and key indicators

The objective of this study is to test hypotheses about the ethical impacts (environmental and social equity) of AI in energy transitions. For this, we applied two panel regressions to analyze the ethical impact of AI on the environment and social equity. The dependent variables represent the ethical outcomes influenced by AI in energy transitions.

The empirical analysis carried out is applied to USA, UK, Japan and EU situations and includes annual data for each variable for the period 2014-2022. Selecting the USA, UK, Japan, and the EU as focal points for studying the ethical impacts of AI in energy transmission offers a comprehensive view into how diverse regulatory environments, technological advancements, and societal values shape ethical AI implementations. The USA has a robust AI ecosystem driven by major tech companies and significant government interest in AI for energy management. However, regulation is still developing, leading to unique ethical discussions about balancing innovation with data privacy, environmental impact, and corporate responsibility (Silva, 2023). The UK's approach is characterized by stringent ethical guidelines and a focus on transparent AI usage within its energy sector. The UK government actively works on policies related to data security, transparency, and environmental sustainability, making it an interesting case for studying ethical AI frameworks in energy systems (Ahmad et al., 2021). Japan emphasizes AI ethics with cultural nuances, prioritizing harmony and societal well-being. Japan's energy AI landscape involves balancing technological advancements with deep-rooted ethical principles, especially given its dependence on energy imports and vulnerability to natural disasters that affect energy infrastructure (Silva, 2023). The EU is a leader in ethical AI regulations, with strict guidelines prioritizing data privacy, transparency, and sustainability. The EU's regulatory framework for AI in energy transmission emphasizes ethical responsibility, making it a model for developing ethical AI applications that balance efficiency with social and environmental impacts (EPRS, 2020). The description of the variables is given in Table 1.

This study measures the environmental impact of AI as the dependent variable in the first model through the CO₂ emissions, which serve as a robust measure of environmental effect, given their direct linkage to energy-based environmental degradation. In the second model, the dependent variable, social equity in energy, is proxied by the primary energy consumption per capita, which reflects baseline access and equity, allowing identification of disparities in energy accessibility. As independent variables, to measure the level of AI adoption, i.e., the technological advancements influencing energy efficiency and innovation, we use as a proxy the energy technology RD&D budgets (financial allocations dedicated to advancing various energy technologies). To represent the technological sophistication and AI-related infrastructure within an economy, impacting both efficiency and energy equity, we use high-technology exports data. In order to analyse the ethical impacts (environmental and social equity) of AI

in energy transitions, control variables are used in the regression models to add value and certainty to the models. Failure to do so could lead to biased tests. The renewable energy share controls for the shift toward renewable resources, an essential factor in reducing emissions and promoting equitable energy distribution, showing the energy sector development. The energy intensity reflects the energy efficiency of economic activities, crucial for understanding the environmental footprint. The GDP growth indicates economic capacity, accounting for differences in energy demand due to developmental stages, which affects both emissions and access equity.

Table 1. Description of variables in the study

Indicators	Description	Source
Dependent variable (model 1)		
Carbon dioxide emissions from energy (CO ₂)	Million tonnes of carbon dioxide. It is the proxy for the environmental impact	2024 Energy Institute Statistical Review of World Energy energyinst.org
Dependent variable (model 2)		
Primary energy: Consumption per capita (En_cons)	Gigajoule per capita. It is the proxy for the social equity in energy	2024 Energy Institute Statistical Review of World Energy energyinst.org
Independent variables		
Energy technology RD&D budget NC (millions) (RD&D)	This includes all RD&D (Research, Development, and Deployment) programmes that concern one of the following seven main branches of energy-related developments, as collected by the IEA, which are: (i) energy efficiency; (ii) fossil fuels (oil, gas and coal); (iii) renewables; (iv) nuclear fission and fusion; (v) hydrogen and fuel cells; (vi) other power and storage techniques; and (vii) other cross-cutting technologies or research (IEA). It is the proxy for AI adoption rate in energy.	Energy Technology RD&D Budgets (2024 edition) IEA
High-technology exports (% of manufactured exports) (Hi_tech)	Are products with high R&D intensity, such as in aerospace, computers, pharmaceuticals, scientific instruments, and electrical machinery.	IEA
Control variables		
Energy intensity level of primary energy (MJ/\$2017 PPP GDP) (En_intens)	This is the ratio of energy supply to GDP at purchasing power parity. Energy intensity measures how much energy producing one economic output requires. A lower ratio means less energy is required per unit of output.	World Bank
Renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation (%) (Renew_en)	Degree of renewable energy integration, such as the percentage of energy from renewable sources.	IRENA
GDP growth (GDP_growth)	GDP growth rate at market prices in constant local currency. Constant 2015 U.S. dollar pricing are used for aggregates.	World Bank

Source: authors' processing

3.2. Panel data model

The objective of the study is to test hypotheses about the ethical impacts (environmental and social equity) of AI in energy transitions. The data sample in this study is panel data, i.e. cross-sectional time-

series data. The analysis of panel data involves three more or less independent approaches: pooled ordinary least squares (POLS) models; fixed effects models (FE); random effects models (RE).

The choice between these methods depends on the objective of the analysis and the exogeneity issues of the explanatory variables. Therefore, the aim is to choose and fit a regression model that is appropriate for the panel data sets in the sample of this study. The application of the methods was performed using the Eviews 10 software.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Tests for cross-sectional dependence, stationarity and panel cointegration

The analysis starts by testing the cross-sectional dependence of the data sets, for both models (the results are given in table 2). The residual cross-section dependence test checks for cross-sectional dependence or correlation in the residuals of a panel dataset. This is important because cross-sectional dependence can affect the validity of inferences in panel data models. The Pesaran CD test was applied because it has good properties for the panels with both small cross-sections and time dimensions (Tugcu, 2018). The general null hypothesis for this test is that no cross-sectional dependence exists in the data.

Table 2. Residual Cross-Section Dependence Test*

Test	Model	Statistic	Prob.
Pesaran CD	Model 1	-0.173	0.863
Pesaran CD	Model 2	5.074	0.000

Null hypothesis*: No cross-section dependence (correlation) in residuals

Source: own calculations, using Eviews 10 software

For model 1, the high p-value strongly suggests no cross-sectional dependence, as the null hypothesis is not rejected. For model 2, the Pesaran CD test shows a very low p-value, indicating significant cross-sectional dependence and providing strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence, confirming the presence of cross-sectional dependence in the residuals of the panel data model. Regarding the condition of stationarity of the data sets, if this is not met, then the problem of spurious regression may arise and the estimated parameters may be biased. This study used the Levin-Lin-Chu ADF (Levin et al., 2002) panel-based unit root test. The results showed that all variables are stationary at the level or the first difference. To test the panel cointegration, we applied the Kao Residual Cointegration Test. The results are presented in table 3. The Kao test examines the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration between variables. Both models have p-values of 0.000, which are below typical significance levels (e.g., 0.05 or 0.01). This leads us to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration, suggesting a long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables in both models. The ADF test is used to determine the presence of unit roots, testing the stationarity of residuals. The significant values for RESID(-1) in both models confirm that the residuals are stationary, supporting the cointegration results from the Kao test. The results indicate a significant cointegration relationship for both models, with residual stationarity, reinforcing the findings. This study can therefore proceed with the panel regression model.

4.2. Application of the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares - POLS regression model

The key assumption of this model is that there are no unique attributes of individuals within the measurement set and no universal effects over time. The POLS regression model is applied to the entire sample of states, neglecting the cross-sectional and time-series nature of the data; therefore, by default it is assumed that all parameters of the zone-specific regression equations in the sample, including the constants, are approximately of the same value.

In the first model regression, the R^2 value is 0.98, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.098, which corresponds to a very strong relationship between the dependent variable, CO2 emissions, and independent and control variables. The F -test in the regression yielded a test statistic of 388.62 with an associated probability (p) value of 0, which leads us to conclude that the model coefficient estimates are statistically significant at the 1% level. The model 1 shows that energy intensity level of primary energy, GDP growth, high-

technology exports, RD&D programmes and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are all statistically significant predictors of CO2 emissions. However, it's notable that renewable energy share has a positive relationship with CO2 emissions, which may imply complexities in the way renewable energy is deployed or measured. The high R-squared value suggests a very strong fit, meaning the model explains most of the variance in CO2 emissions.

Table 3. Kao Residual Cointegration Test* and Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation**

Kao Residual Cointegration Test				
Model 1				
Test Statistic (ADF)	-3.699			
Probability (Prob.)	0.000			
Model 2				
Test Statistic (ADF)	-3.873			
Probability (Prob.)	0.000			
Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test Equation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Model 1				
RESID(-1)	-1.224	0.233	-5.256	0.000
D(RESID(-1))	0.534	0.204	2.609	0.014
Model 2				
RESID(-1)	-1.523	0.266	-5.709	0.000
D(RESID(-1))	0.517	0.201	2.573	0.016
Statistic		Value		
		Model 1	Model 2	
R-squared		0.521	0.587	
Adjusted R-squared		0.503	0.571	
S.E. of regression		82.165	3.322	
Sum squared resid		175529.7	286.972	
Log likelihood		-162.137	-72.310	
Durbin-Watson stat		2.145	2.105	
Mean dependent var		10.030	0.204	
S.D. dependent var		116.573	5.077	
Akaike info criterion		11.724	5.307	
Schwarz criterion		11.819	5.403	
Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.753	5.337	

Null Hypothesis*: No cointegration

Method**: Least Squares

Source: own calculations, using Eviews 10 software

In the second model regression, the R^2 value is 0.94, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.093, which corresponds to a very good fit between the dependent variable, primary energy consumption, and independent and control variables. The F -test in the regression yielded a test statistic of 99.64 with an associated probability (p) value of 0, showing that the model as a whole is highly statistically significant. The model 2 shows that energy intensity level of primary energy and high-technology exports are significant predictors of energy consumption, with energy intensity showing the strongest effect. GDP growth, RD&D programmes and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are not statistically significant predictors of energy consumption in this dataset.

While in general POLS regression model satisfies the adequacy conditions, as evidenced by the results obtained, the main problem with this model is that it does not distinguish between cross-sections (regions) in the sample, and by combining all regions in this pooled panel it rejects heterogeneity or individuality that may exist.

The following sections will fit a fixed effects model on the same sample data and compare the fit of the two models.

4.3. Application of the Fixed Effects (FE) regression model

The key assumption of this model is that there are unique attributes of cross-sections that do not vary over time. That is, unique attributes for a given individual i are time t invariant. These attributes may or may not be correlated with the dependent variables.

Therefore, a fixed effects regression model that takes into account heterogeneity or individuality across regions in the sample is applied. The term fixed effects is due to the fact that although the constant may differ across regions under the influence of various specific factors, it does not vary over time and is considered time invariant.

The following empirical models are estimated:

$$\text{Model 1: } CO2_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RD\&D_{it} + \beta_2 Hi_tech_{it} + \beta_3 X_{it} + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Model 2: } En_cons_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RD\&D_{it} + \beta_2 Hi_tech_{it} + \beta_3 X_{it} + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where: $CO2$ is the carbon dioxide emissions from energy (proxy for environmental impact), i and t refer to regions and years, respectively, En_cons is the primary energy: consumption per capita (proxy for the social equity in energy), $RD\&D$ includes all RD&D programmes that concern one of the seven main branches of energy-related developments (proxy for AI adoption rate in energy), Hi_tech is the high-technology exports (% of manufactured exports) (proxy for the technological sophistication and AI-related infrastructure within an economy), X is a vector of control variables: energy intensity level of primary energy (En_intens); renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation (%) ($Renew_en$); GDP growth (GDP_growth) and ε is the error term. The period fixed effects are included to account for the impact of time-varying factors affecting all regions (μ_t).

The values of R^2 (0,997 for both models) and adjusted R^2 (0,997 for model 1 and 0,996 for model 2) correspond to a very strong relationship between the variables. The F -test in the regression yielded a test statistic of 1572.48 for model 1 and 1278,47 for model 2 with an associated probability (p) value of 0, confirming that the overall models are highly significant. The first model shows that energy intensity level of primary energy, GDP growth, and high-technology exports are significant predictors of CO2 emissions, with energy intensity and GDP growth positively associated with CO2, while high-technology exports shows a negative association. The R&D expenditure and renewable energy effects are less clear, with renewable energy showing a weak positive association with CO2 emissions, which may require further exploration. The second model shows that energy intensity, GDP growth, and high-technology exports are significant predictors of energy consumption, with energy intensity and GDP growth positively associated and high-technology exports negatively associated, suggesting that technological expenditures reduce energy consumption. RD&D programmes and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are not statistically significant predictors of energy consumption in this context.

4.4. Comparison of the POLS model with the FE model

In order to choose which model is more appropriate, namely the POLS or the FE fixed effects model, the following hypothesis are tested:

- H_0 : POLS is the best model if the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, i.e. if the null hypothesis is accepted;
- H_1 : FE is the best model if the alternative hypothesis is accepted, or if the null hypothesis is rejected.

In order to test these hypotheses, the Reduntant likelihood test is applied. This test determines if fixed effects (differences across cross-sections) are necessary in the model. The results of this test are presented in Table 4.

Since the associated cross-section probabilities F are 0 (less than 0.05), we reject the null hypothesis that fixed effects are redundant. This implies that fixed effects significantly improve the models, and

cross-sectional differences are important to consider. Similarly, the Chi-square tests confirms the significance of fixed effects. Therefore, the conclusion of the tests is that the fixed-effects (FE) models are more appropriate for the sample data in this study than the POLS model, because region-specific characteristics are present, constant over time.

Table 4. Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Model 1			
Cross-section F	54.893	(3,27)	0.000
Cross-section Chi-square	70.560	3	0.000
Model 2			
Cross-section F	185.153	(3,27)	0.000
Cross-section Chi-square	110.57	3	0.000

Source: own calculations, using Eviews 10 software

The redundant fixed effects tests indicate that fixed effects are necessary, justifying the inclusion of cross-sectional differences. The first model shows that energy intensity level of primary energy, GDP growth, high-technology exports, and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are significant predictors of CO2 emissions. However, the positive coefficient on renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation is unexpected, as it implies an increase in CO2 emissions, potentially due to specific characteristics of renewable energy deployment or measurement. The model has a high explanatory power, as evidenced by the R-squared value. The second fixed effects model indicates that energy intensity level of primary energy and high-technology exports are significant predictors of energy consumption, with energy intensity having the strongest positive association. GDP growth, RD&D programmes, and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are not statistically significant predictors in this model. The high R-squared value suggests that the model explains most of the variation in energy consumption across cross-sections, although the low Durbin-Watson statistic implies possible autocorrelation.

4.5. Application of the Random Effects (RE) regression model

No variation was attributed to the period effect (S.D. = 0.000, Rho = 0.000), implying no significant random effect due to time. For the first model, the S.D. of the idiosyncratic random effect is 227.141 with Rho = 1.000, indicating that individual-specific random effects are entirely responsible for the variance in CO2 emissions in this model. For the second model, the S.D. of the idiosyncratic random effect is 5.503, with Rho = 1.000, indicating that individual-specific random effects fully account for the variation in energy consumption in this model.

4.6. Comparing the fixed effects model with the random effects model

The Hausman test assesses whether the fixed effects or random effects model is more appropriate by testing if the unique errors are correlated with the regressors. A significant test result suggests that the fixed effects model is preferable. The results are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

For model 1, the p-value is 0.058, which is slightly above the 5% significance level. This result suggests weak evidence against the random effects model. At a 5% level, we would fail to reject the null hypothesis, implying that the random effects model might be appropriate. However, the closeness of the p-value to 0.05 could also justify considering the fixed effects model, especially in cases where conservative decision-making is preferred. The table compares the coefficients for each variable under fixed and random effects models to assess their stability. Key variables are compared, showing minor differences in estimated coefficients across models. The fixed effects model shows that energy intensity level of primary energy, GDP growth, high-technology exports, RD&D programmes, and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are significant predictors of CO2 emissions. The high R-squared value (0.986) indicates that this model explains most of the variation in CO2 emissions. The positive association of renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation with CO2 emissions is unexpected, suggesting further investigation into how renewable energy is implemented or measured.

Table 5. The Hausman test for model 1 (Dependent Variable: CO2)

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic		Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random	10.696		5	0.058
	Fixed Effects	Random Effects	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
Period random effects test comparisons				
EN_INTENS	2211.994	2299.605	3121.371	0.116
GDP_GROWTH	66.749	31.917	766.968	0.208
HIGH_TECH_EXP	-113.453	-104.308	39.952	0.147
RD_D	-0.004	-0.003	0.000	0.373
RENEW_EN	50.504	62.818	62.410	0.119
Period random effects test equation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-3890.114	987.054	-3.941	0.001
EN_INTENS	2211.995	114.035	19.397	0.000
GDP_GROWTH	66.749	30.399	2.195	0.038
HIGH_TECH_EXP	-113.453	18.407	-6.163	0.000
RD_D	-0.004	0.001	-6.456	0.000
RENEW_EN	50.504	12.392	4.075	0.001

Source: own calculations, using Eviews 10 software

Table 6. The Hausman test for model 2 (Dependent Variable: EN_CONS)

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic		Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random	264.353732		5	0.0000
	Fixed Effects	Random Effects	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
Period random effects test comparisons				
EN_INTENS	63.183	80.495	1.832	0.000
GDP_GROWTH	-1.740	0.506	0.450	0.001
HIGH_TECH_EXP	2.525	3.689	0.023	0.000
RD_D	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000
RENEW_EN	-2.30305	0.350	0.036	0.000
Period random effects test equation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-12.738	23.917	-0.532	0.599
EN_INTENS	63.183	2.763	22.865	0.000
GDP_GROWTH	-1.740	0.736	-2.362	0.027
HIGH_TECH_EXP	2.525	0.446	5.661	0.000
RD_D	-0.000	0.000	-11.241	0.000
RENEW_EN	-2.301	0.300	-7.663	0.000

Source: own calculations, using Eviews 10 software

For model 2, the low p-value (0.000) suggests that we reject the null hypothesis of no difference between the fixed and random effects models. This means that the fixed effects model is more appropriate for this data, as it indicates the presence of correlation between the regressors and the individual-specific effects. The table 6 displays the estimated coefficients under both the fixed and random effects assumptions, along with the differences in their variances (Var(Diff)) and the probability values (Prob) for each variable. All show significant differences between the fixed and random effects coefficients (p-value = 0.000 for each variable), further supporting the choice of the fixed effects model. The Hausman test supports the use of the fixed effects model, suggesting that individual-specific effects are correlated with the regressors. The fixed effects model shows that energy intensity level of primary energy, GDP growth, high-technology exports, RD&D programmes, and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation are significant predictors of energy consumption. Notably, energy

intensity level of primary energy and high-technology exports positively affect energy consumption, while GDP growth and renewable energy share of electricity capacity and generation have a negative effect. The high R-squared value (0.995) indicates that the model explains nearly all the variation in energy consumption across cross-sections.

5. Conclusions

This study examined the ethical impacts of AI, measured through proxies like energy technology R&D budget and high-tech exports, on environmental and social equity aspects of energy transitions by conducting two panel regressions. The first model related to the environmental impact showed that the significant findings on CO₂ emissions highlight both positive and negative ethical implications. The positive impacts can be justified by the fact that the role of high-technology exports and R&D investment in reducing CO₂ emissions suggests that AI-driven technologies, through improved energy efficiency and innovation, could potentially mitigate environmental harm by reducing reliance on carbon-intensive sources. On the contrary, the increase in emissions with higher energy intensity and GDP growth underscores AI's role in accelerating energy demand, which could exacerbate environmental harm. The unexpected positive relationship between renewable energy usage and CO₂ emissions indicates potential inefficiencies in renewable deployment, possibly due to indirect emissions from renewable technology production or infrastructure demands, raising questions on the actual carbon-saving potential of AI-integrated renewables. Regarding the first model appropriateness, the random effects model was selected, though results were close to supporting the fixed effects model, especially for conservative approaches. Energy intensity, GDP growth and renewable energy share were significant drivers of CO₂ emissions. Notably, renewable energy's positive association with emissions suggests complexities in its deployment or measurement. The high R-squared (98.69%) suggests this model strongly explains the variance in emissions, making it robust in predicting environmental impacts in AI-led energy shifts.

The second model related to the social equity in energy impact (proxied by the energy consumption per capita, representing baseline energy access disparities), the results reveal contrasting effects on energy equity. The positive impacts are explained by the fact that the decrease in energy consumption with GDP growth and renewable energy usage implies that AI in advanced economies or efficient renewable deployment might support equitable energy access, aligning with social equity goals. But the negative impacts come from the findings according to which the positive correlation between energy intensity and consumption suggested that AI might indirectly perpetuate inequality in energy access, as high-energy consumption areas may still consume disproportionately, leaving others underserved. Regarding the model appropriateness, the Hausman test recommended the fixed effects model due to significant individual-specific effects. AI-driven high-tech expenditure and energy intensity promoted energy consumption, while GDP growth and renewable energy use reduced it, hinting at a nuanced role for renewable energy in equitable access. With an R-squared of 99.57%, this model explains most variance in energy consumption, showcasing a strong fit.

The study's findings are significant because they reveal the dual impact of artificial intelligence (AI) in energy transitions, affecting both environmental sustainability and social equity. By analysing AI's influence on CO₂ emissions, the study highlights how advanced technologies can both mitigate and exacerbate environmental impacts, depending on their application. This underscores AI's potential to reduce emissions through efficient energy use while also raising concerns about increased energy demand from accelerated economic activities. Furthermore, the findings emphasize the importance of equitable energy distribution. While AI advancements can support energy access in developed regions, they may also widen energy consumption disparities in less developed areas. These results contribute to a nuanced understanding of AI's ethical implications in energy transitions, stressing the need for policy frameworks that balance innovation with sustainability and fairness. This is crucial as AI becomes increasingly integrated into the global energy landscape, impacting both ecological and social dimensions.

The main limitations of this study could be summarized as follows: the dependent variables – environmental impact measured by CO₂ emissions and social equity through energy consumption per capita – may not fully capture the ethical implications of AI. Using additional or alternative measures

for social equity and environmental impact could provide a more comprehensive view. Moreover, proxies like the energy technology RD&D budget and high-technology exports were used to represent AI adoption. However, these proxies may not entirely reflect AI's influence in the energy sector, as they include broader technological advancements and may introduce biases due to varying rates of technology implementation across regions. The positive association between renewable energy share and CO₂ emissions, though statistically significant, is counterintuitive. This may indicate complexities in renewable energy deployment or unobserved variables that affect emissions outcomes, suggesting the need for further exploration or additional control variables. Also, since the study spans only certain regions or years, this may limit its applicability globally or over longer timescales, especially given the rapid advancements in AI and renewable energy technologies.

In conclusion, while AI adoption has the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions, its relationship with renewable energy demands further exploration. On the social equity side, AI's role may be beneficial by increasing energy access but shows complex interactions with economic growth and renewable energy. These insights can guide policies to optimize AI's ethical impact on energy transitions by balancing environmental concerns and equitable energy access.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Ahmad, T., Zhang, D., Huang, C., Zhang, H., Dai, N., Song, Y., & Chen, H. (2021). Artificial intelligence in sustainable energy industry: Status Quo, challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125834>.
2. Alsaigh, R., Mehmood, R., & Katib, I. (2023). AI explainability and governance in smart energy systems: a review. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 11, 1071291. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2023.1071291>
3. Batool, A., Zowghi, D., & Bano, M. (2023). Responsible AI governance: a systematic literature review. *arXiv preprint*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.10896>
4. Dong, Z., Tan, C., Ma, B., & Ning, Z. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence on the energy transition: The role of regulatory quality as a guardrail, not a wall. *Energy Economics*, 140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107988>
5. Dinca, Z., Oprean-Stan, C., & Balsalobre-Lorente, D. (2025). UK Carbon Price Dynamics: Long-Memory Effects and AI-Based Forecasting. *Fractal and Fractional*, 9(6), 350. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fractalfract9060350>
6. Energy Institute Statistical Review of World Energy. (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.energyinst.org/statistical-review/home>
7. Energy Technology RD&D Budgets. (2024 edition). Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-product/energy-technology-rd-and-d-budget-database-2>
8. EPRS. (2020). *The ethics of artificial intelligence: Issues and Initiatives*. European Parliamentary Research Service, March 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2861/6644>. Retrieved from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/634452/EPRS_STU\(2020\)634452_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/634452/EPRS_STU(2020)634452_EN.pdf) (accessed on 07.07.2025)
9. IRENA. (2024). *Renewable Energy Statistics 2024*. The International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi. Retrieved from <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2024/Jul/Renewable-energy-statistics-2024> (accessed on 09.07.2025)
10. Kyriakarakos, G. (2025). Artificial Intelligence and the Energy Transition. *Sustainability*, 17(3), 1140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17031140>

11. Li, W., Li, J.-P., Wang, Y.-F., & Stan, S.-E. (2025). Is artificial intelligence an impediment or an impetus to renewable energy investment? Evidence from China. *Energy Economics*, 147, 108550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2025.108550>
12. Li, H., Lu, Z., Zhang, Z., & Tănăsescu, C. (2025). How does artificial intelligence affect manufacturing firms' energy intensity? *Energy Economics*, 141, 108109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.108109>
13. OECD. (2024). *Defining AI incidents and related terms*. OECD Artificial Intelligence Papers, No. 16, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/d1a8d965-en>
14. Silva, N. (2023). *The Ethical and Social Implications of Using AI for Energy Management*. Retrieved from <https://energycentral.com/c/iu/ethical-and-social-implications-using-ai-energy-management>
15. Tugcu, C.T. (2018). *Panel Data Analysis in the Energy-Growth Nexus (EGN)* (Chapter 8). In: Menegaki, A.N. (ed.). *The Economics and Econometrics of the Energy-Growth Nexus*. Academic Press, 255-271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812746-9.00008-0>
16. Verdecchia, R., Sallou, J. & Cruz, L. (2023). A Systematic Review of Green AI. *arXiv preprint*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.11047>
17. Wang, Q., Li, Y., & Li, R. (2024). Ecological footprints, carbon emissions, and energy transitions: The impact of artificial intelligence (AI). *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11, 1043. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03520-5>
18. Winsta, J. (2025). The Hidden Costs of AI: A Review of Energy, E-Waste, and Inequality in Model Development. *arXiv preprint*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.09611v1>
19. Xu, Y., Shao, X., & Tănăsescu, C. (2024). How are artificial intelligence, carbon market, and energy sector connected? A systematic analysis of time-frequency spillovers. *Energy Economics*, 132, 107477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107477>
20. Zhang, X., Khan, K., Shao, X., Oprean-Stan, C., & Zhang, Q. (2024). The rising role of artificial intelligence in renewable energy development in China. *Energy Economics*, 132, 107489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107489>
21. Zhao, Q., Wang, L., Stan, S.-E., & Mirza, N. (2024). Can artificial intelligence help accelerate the transition to renewable energy? *Energy Economics*, 134, 107584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107584>.

© 2025 by the authors. This work is openly licensed under CC BY 4.0. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).